

METHODOLOGY OF PREPARING FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC COMPETENCIES

Tuxtayeva Nilufar Achilovna

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Teacher of the “Theoretical aspects of English language” department

nilufartuxtayeva0609@gmail.com

Abstract: Nowadays, applying linguistic competence in the education system offers a method to this issue with the help of the formation of special, general and key competencies. Moreover, the development of linguistic competence of future language teachers contains a variety of private methodological competencies. One of the competencies is linguistics which assures a teacher’s willingness to teach the language. This investigation reveals the significance of linguistic competence in assuring the improvement of a new quality of education. The basic goal of this research paper is to identify principles and develop strategies for the establishment of future teachers’ linguistic competence in the context of the continuous pedagogical sphere.

Keywords: *Linguistic competence, development, teaching and learning language, education, principles and tactics of linguistic training, educational resources, future language teachers.*

Аннотация: В настоящее время применение языковой компетентности в системе образования предлагает метод решения данного вопроса с помощью формирования специальных, общих и ключевых компетенций. Более того, развитие лингвистической компетентности будущих учителей языка содержит в себе множество частных методических компетенций. Одной из компетенций является лингвистика, которая обеспечивает желание учителя преподавать язык. Данное исследование раскрывает значение языковой компетентности в обеспечении повышения нового качества образования. Основная цель данной исследовательской работы – выявление принципов и разработка стратегии формирования языковой компетентности будущих учителей в условиях непрерывной педагогической сферы.

Ключевые слова: *Языковая компетентность, развитие, преподавание и изучение языка, образование, принципы и тактика языковой подготовки, образовательные ресурсы, будущие учителя языка.*

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi vaqtda ta'lim tizimida lingvistik kompetentsiyani qo'llash maxsus, umumiy va asosiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish yordamida ushbu masalani hal qilish usulini taklif qiladi. Bundan tashqari, bo'lajak til o'qituvchilarining lingvistik kompetentsiyasini rivojlantirish turli xil shaxsiy uslubiy kompetensiyalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Qobiliyatlardan biri bu tilshunoslik bo'lib, o'qituvchining tilni o'rgatishga tayyorligini ta'minlaydi. Ushbu tadqiqot ta'limning yangi sifatini oshirishni ta'minlashda

lingvistik kompetentsiyaning ahamiyatini ochib beradi. Ushbu tadqiqot ishining asosiy maqsadi - uzluksiz pedagogik soha kontekstida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning lingvistik kompetentsiyasini shakllantirish tamoyillarini aniqlash va strategiyalarni ishlab chiqish.

Kalit so'zlar: *Lingvistik kompetentsiya, tilni rivojlantirish, o'qitish va o'rganish, ta'lim, lingvistik tayyorgarlik tamoyillari va taktikasi, ta'lim resurslari, bo'lajak o'qituvchilar.*

Introduction

In the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages, the need to educate a new type of specialist with a high culture of interpersonal communication as an integral element of not only general and professional culture, but also high professional and social competencies are determined by the requirements of modern society and the labour market. This is not only the acquisition of modern professional knowledge, but also the use of new approaches to the training of highly qualified specialists who can use various language tools in independent expression, to have the methodology of teaching foreign languages in professional activities. In this regard, one of the solutions to the tasks set before the educational institutions is the introduction of the final goal of training future English language teachers in the educational process, a competency-oriented approach to the future profession.

In the context of the integration of the higher professional education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan into the global educational space, the need for students of higher education institutions to acquire linguistic competences in organizing their professional activities has increased significantly. The implementation of large-scale socio-economic complex programs within the framework of cooperation with experts from foreign countries has made the problem of high-quality acquisition of English, one of the world languages, a tool of intercultural communication to achieve educational and professional goals. The above mentioned formation of students' skills of effective communication with colleagues on professional issues; succeed in communicating and exchanging ideas; able to express one's opinion literately and defend one's point of view; requires the need to work with scientifically and professionally important information, and all this is considered the most important component of professional skills of a specialist in any field of activity. Today, when "scientific activity (in various forms) is taking on a wide scale, the task of educating the culture of scientific thinking is more urgent than ever, it is inextricably linked with the task of educating the culture of scientific speech [9]. The professional activity of future teachers is identified by the significant amount of drills they teach, and the professional competence of future teachers carries a group of psychological pedagogical and particular methodological competencies. One of these capabilities is linguistic and methodological, which inabilities the teacher's willingness to teach the language to elementary school pupils. Linguistic and methodological competence is realized as a skill to perfectly perform methodological tasks and activities on language education of primary schoolchildren in a new data atmosphere based on

acquired awareness and first endure and concerning the requirements of the standards [4;12]. All that as a whole checks a full achievements of competency-based sample for training of bachelor’s students studying in teacher education. The showing conflicts established the significance of the topic of investigation.

Successful professional activity of a foreign language teacher involves the possession of a fairly extensive amount of lexical material and free operation of them in the process of pedagogical activity. The teacher is faced with various problems, new situations that require a certain speech reaction and various knowledge in his daily teaching practice:

- How to act as a teacher?
- Should he/she limit set of typical phrases?

The opportunity to use a foreign language as a means of communication and have a friendly conversation with students and jointly resolve a problem, including one that is not necessarily related to educational material will be missed [1]. The analysis of the results of teaching practice by students at school showed that the future teacher doesn’t always manage to use specific reasons for unprepared speech, create natural atmosphere in the lesson, ensure adequate response to a situation that goes beyond educational topics (lateness, cheating, scattering attention of students, etc.). Language Methodists noted that while teaching teacher face experience during the practice, some difficulties in communicating with the class, pointed to the "lack of lexical units" [6,376].

Literature review

Investigation learns on the recognition of strategies and tactics in the last decades that establish the capabilities which get ready pedagogical university students to perform their professional activity has become applicable. In the area of language teaching it is particularly related to linguistic and methodological competence. Lvov (2007) investigated the components of competence. He differentiated personal qualities such as philological education, speech culture, spiritual and educational interests etc.; and professional qualities that contain subject awareness, an skill to write compositions, work with texts etc., and methodological abilities, i.e. to select studying materials and apply them appropriately, to recognize the causes for learners’ gaps in awareness and their abilities, to correct and prevent them [1;12]. Sinichkina (2010) gives information about linguistic and methodological competence on the based on the system of professional competence of a language teacher and distinguishes its basic components: axiological, cognitive, and operational tasks [9;54]. As stated in author, they serve as a vector for the establishing of linguistic and methodological competence, identifying the goal and structure of the future pedagogical activity of a language teacher.

An investigation by Isaeva (2016) pays attention on the formation of linguistic and methodological competence among future teachers of Russian language. The scientist develops two key strategies for linguistic and methodological training of bachelor’s, ensuring the development of linguistic and methodological thinking and readiness for practical activities in teaching language to schoolchildren in the context of new standards

introduction. The issues of linguistic and methodological competence formation are also considered in the context of professional training of primary school teachers [7;214].

On this way, we are especially engaged in the learning of Kurlygina (2012). The scientist carries out a component examination of teacher in the methodological activities with connection to the competencies that inability the establishment of linguistic and methodological competence. Based on linguistic and methodological competence formation, the scientist thinks linguistic and methodological exercises as models of authentic pedagogical cases that ensure the first (starting) readiness of a pedagogical university graduate for methodological tasks in teaching foreign language to school pupils [10;369].

The problems of successful professional training of teachers are thoroughly learned by foreign investigators. A scientific review of articles on teacher training from 2000 to 2010 is showed in the publication written by Avalos (2011). In the article, the linguists gave the opinion about how the production leads to the compounding of teacher professional learning and how investigation and achievement have possess cognizance of these causes and supported food for good things and optimism about their results, although not yet about their sustainability in time [8;40].

The research of Opfer and Pedder (2011) is devoted to the issues of teacher professional achievement, the linguist differentiate three subsystems - teacher, school, and learning activity - and depicts how results of these subsystems encourage and can be combined in different methods. As a result, they influence teacher learning with a varying intensity. The authors conclude that to comprehend teacher learning researchers must use methodological practices that attention to the reciprocal affects of all three subsystems [8;376].

Professional competence was a topic of investigation in the study done by Dante Guerrero and Gerson La Rosa (2013). In the scientific research, the authors gives an information about an estimation of the intellectual content of investigation connected to teacher professional competence. Applying scientific domain analysis, a new paradigm of data science, the scientists studied a number of scientific articles in journals listed in the multidisciplinary databases: “Web of Science” and “Scopus” from 1950 to mid-2012. The generating scientific map applies the scientific visualization software “Citespace II” promotes visualizing the topic of investigation, special qualities and professional competences’ ways. As part of our experiment in preparation for pedagogical practice, we decided to test according to students' knowledge of the English vocabulary of everyday life. We also wanted to check the level of students' ability to be adequate speech partner when resolving non-standard situations, for example, if it is necessary, adjust discipline in the classroom.

Methodology

The investigation applies a complicated of theoretical and practical teaching ways: examination of the theory and practice of teaching, instruction of lower grades in the mode of course preparation; bachelor students and teachers examination for the

purpose of establishing their linguistic and methodological competence; examining of teachers’ and students’ lessons. The requirements to develop the linguistic and methodological competence of in-service teachers is identified by the examining of their lessons. The subsequent comparative examining of two lessons of two different teachers (teacher 1, teacher 2) on the similar theme of lesson depicts the important role of linguistic and methodological competence in assuring the sufficient of the foreign language lesson on developing subject and meta-subject results.

The plans of the lessons of both teachers are based on activity paradigm. Instructors do not presents the theoretical rule directly, however establish the procedure so that students find and develop a new spelling rule. From the didactic point of view, all stages of the new knowledge acquisition are consistently maintained in teacher A’s and teacher B’s lessons. However, in the teacher A’s lesson, children are more cognitive, independent in their opinions; they carry out analytical work with language material, and consciously formulate the rule through a set of questions, etc. It can be confidently said that the teacher A’s lesson on the achievement of subject and meta-subject results is more effective. In terms of linguistic correctness and methodological literacy, the teacher B’s lesson is in many ways inferior [4;293].

We begin with the stage of knowledge actualization. Teacher A chooses only four words for work, each of them has only one orthogram, which pupils must determine and correctly solve the spelling problem through the selection of a check word. However, when working with these four words, the teacher repeats a large amount of information, and moreover, makes an important generalization: two different orthograms (checked unstressed vowels in the word root and paired voiced and deaf consonants in the word root), and only one way to solve a spelling task [4;470].

Results

Acknowledgement stage of the experiment. Educational institutes suggests many advanced training programs, which contain educational program on the development of certain competencies of teachers. Teachers had to select the attention of training that they requires most (without reference to the course dates and location). Suggesting most famous courses among primary school teachers are:

- a) Development of future teachers’ subject competence (15%);
- b) Growth of primary future teachers’ methodological competence (12%);
- c) Improvement of future teachers’ subject, methodological, psychological, pedagogical, and communicative competencies (14%);
- d) Increasing future teachers’ skills for improvement of meta-subject skills in students (15%);
- e) Improvement of future teachers’ assessment ability (9%).

So, the conducting survey depicts that teachers require to develop their subject and methodological skills. The professional activity of primary school teachers is multi-subject. Hence, teachers had to determine their particular methodological abilities [3;12].

In the theory and methodology of foreign language education, the main conditions for the process of teaching foreign language professionally-oriented vocabulary are identified:

- highlighting the lexical features of the material intended for study in the procedure of preparing for classes;
- focusing students' attention on both methodological and didactic aspects of the lesson;
- the presence of a professionally oriented system of student activities in the classroom (for example, self-preparation, students conducting fragments of the lesson, their comprehensive analysis, identifying errors and searching for their possible causes;
- developing options for test tasks by the students;
- questions on the topic under study and their discussion;
- the creation of visual aids on the studied topic and their presentation) [10;20].

It is especially important to increase the level of motivation of students, it is used in the classroom, in particular, in home reading, professionally directed literature, which emphasizes the importance of the teacher's work. We understood that the lists of components activation of the professional and pedagogical orientation of training should not be applied sporadically, but purposefully and systematically within the whole range of studies at the university [2;470]. As the criteria for selecting texts were:

- relevance, authenticity, cognition, informativeness and the content of the text (story is fascinating/ the story has an interesting plot from the point of view of young people);
- educational professional orientation;
- composite rational design; - compliance with the level of language for student preparation (the language is not too complicated for students, it is modern and time distance does not interfere with the perception of the text) [5;55].

The selection also take into account [8;40] the frequency and repetition of lexical material in texts and its use in the professional field. Special presence in the text of the main categories of the terminological apparatus of the future teacher of a foreign language was important. Therefore, as one of the main principles of our technology was the principle of integration of the pragmatic setting "Language for real communication" with an analytical approach to working with a literary text.

I. Conclusion

It has been formed that the establishing of linguistic and methodological competence among learners and its development among future teachers will be successful if cognitive and projective strategies are applied in university programs and in advanced training courses for teachers. Generalization of the results obtained in the study allows us to formulate the following conclusions.

1. Professional lexical competence of future teacher of a foreign language as a significant integrative quality of a linguistic personality can be formed in the process of working with professional mentally relevant texts on home reading research institute in a specialized pedagogical university.

2. The author's technology for the formation of professional lexical competence of the future teacher of a foreign language creates optimal conditions for self-realization of a student in a foreign language pedagogy activities.

3. The developed model for the formation of professional lexical competence of the future student, teacher of a foreign language allows teacher to provide the maximum possible transition from educational activity.

REFERENCES

1. Abdukhayotovna A. K. THE ROLE OF AUTHENTIC MATERIALS TO DEVELOP PUPILS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH CLASSES AT ACADEMIC LYCEUMS // Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.

2. Abdukhayotovna A. K. THE IMPLEMENTING OF MOVIE ACTIVITIES TO DEVELOP PUPILS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH CLASSES AT ACADEMIC LYCEUMS // "ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2021. – C. 102-103.

3. Avalos, B. (2011). Teacher professional development in Teaching and Teacher Education over ten years. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 27, 10-20.

4. Barron, B. When smart groups fail / Barron, B. – Stanford. : *The Journal of Learning Sciences*, 12 (3), 2003. – P. 307–359. 2. Cox, E. Adult learners learning from experience : Using a reflective practice model to support work-based learning / Cox, E. – Auckland. : *Reflective Practice*, 6(4), 2005. – P. 459–472.

5. Engle, R. A., and Conant, F.R. Guiding principles for fostering productive disciplinary engagement: Explaining an emergent argument in a community of learners classroom / Engle, R. A., and Conant, F.R. – Auckland.: – *Cognition and Instruction*, 20 (4), 2002. – P. 399 – 483.

6. Kurlygina, O. E. (2012). Methodological task as a means of primary school teachers' linguistic and methodological competence development. PhD Thesis, Moscow.

7. Rinaldi, C. The thought that sustains educational action / Rinaldi, C. – Auckland. : *Reggio Children Newsletter*, 3, 1998. – P. 39–53.

8. Skugarova Yu. V. New life of literary text in teaching foreign languages // *Bulletin. Moscow State University. (Series 19: Linguistics and Intercultural Communication)*. 2002. No. 3. P. 54 - 60.

9. Shamov A. N. Authentic text as a means of improving the lexical aspect of speech in German // *Foreign languages at school*. 2010. No. 7. P. 20 – 26.

10. Sulstonova, N. (2021). MODERNIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 4(9). извлечено от <https://phys-tech.jdpu.uz/index.php/fll/article/view/1989>